

Research

Assessing the Extent and Effects of Vehicles' Noise Pollution and CO Emissions on Human Health in Urban Areas of Faisalabad, Pakistan

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Abstract: *There are so many types of heavy and light traffic vehicles (HTV and LTV), that are moving on the roads in urban areas of Faisalabad, emitting carbon monoxide (CO) and noise in the environment, thus effecting human health. Therefore, noise pollution and CO emissions were measured and assessed using integrating sound level meter (model 6226) and yellow fluke meter, respectively to assess their impacts on human health. Thirty different locations were selected for CO monitoring and forty locations were selected for noise monitoring in whole city. Data was collected in two different times as in the morning and evening. Maximum noise (99 db) was measured in commercial zone in the evening and maximum CO (42 ppm) was measured in industrial zone in the evening time. Questionnaire data that was based on health effects, found that 37% people were affected with noise pollution and 45% people were with respiratory diseases due to CO pollution of vehicular emissions. Similarly, 32% people were affected with allergy, 35% giddiness, 50% ENT (eyes, nose and throat), and 42% people were affected from CO emissions from vehicles emission. Results of the study found maximum locations that were exceeding the standard limit of Environment Protection Agency (EPA) of Pakistan.*

Keywords: *Vehicular emission; CO emission; human health; integrating sound level meter;*

INTRODUCTION

Over population, industrialization, life patterns, and urbanization are the major issues of increasing concentration of urban pollution [1]. Due to over population and migration from rural

to urban areas is the main problem of huge traffic on the roads [2]. According to the United Nations (UN) 54% world population is migrating to urban life [3], that is leading to noise and air pollution [4], especially carbon mono oxide (CO) [5]. Two third of air pollution is caused by vehicular emissions in the urban areas [6]. Whereas, about 97% CO concentration in the air is from the automobile emissions [7]. Noise and air pollution have a co-relation with each other and has combined effect on human health [8], like annoyance [9] and cardiovascular diseases [10-12]. CO is a toxic gas. It decreases the blood hemoglobin; increases blood pressure [13]. Its interaction with hemoglobin is 240 times greater than oxygen. Due to its reactive nature with hemoglobin it transports with the blood, stopping oxygen delivery to the heart, lungs and brain, causing oxygen deficiency, thus effecting these organs and ultimately bring about death with its acute toxicity [14, 15, 16]. According to the European environment agency (TEA) more than 430,000 premature deaths have been reported due to the exposure to air pollution [17], and more than 10,000 early deaths from noise pollution [18].

Faisalabad is the third most populous city and first largest industrial city of Pakistan. It has plain surface and located at 73° 74 longitude in east and 30°31.5 latitude in north, Punjab province [19]. Some areas of this city are very dense and have very narrow roads and congested markets like clock tower. There are so many types of heavy and light traffic vehicles (HTV and LTV), that are moving on the road and emitting CO and noise in the environment, thus effecting human health [20]. Effects on human health such as headache, nuisance and irritation increase due to vehicles' CO emissions and noise pollution during heavy traffic jams in rush hours [21-23]. Specifically, drivers face severe health issues such as stress, headache and arterial pressure and loss of concentration thus effecting driving safety [24-26]. Moreover, automobiles are the major consumer of oxygen as one car is consuming 6000 liters of oxygen in one hour and a single human consumes 30 liters of oxygen [27].

Automobiles are the common source of noise pollution in the urban areas [28,29]. Noise is the undesirable sound that create disturbance in environment and affect human health [30].it is a constant threat to human health [31] and will be permanently sustain because of future transportation development and roads [32-34]. Noise disturbs the body hormone and cause endocrine diseases [35], and its higher-level changes autonomic nervous system, behavior and sympathetic nervous system responses [36]. Temporary or permanent hearing loss can also be the result of exposure to higher (100 dB) noise pollution for longer duration [37]. Therefore, the

exposure level should not exceed 120 dB for more than 30 seconds [38]. Besides numerous other physical health diseases, noise can cause many psychological disorders like sleep disturbance [39-41], irritation, stress [42] and anxiety [43,44].

In developed countries and cities environmentally friendly vehicles such as electric vehicles and hydrogen vehicles are in use to reduce noise pollution and CO emissions. But in developing countries like Pakistan and cities like Faisalabad has a major issue of vehicular emissions and noise pollution due to lack of modern technology and awareness. Hence, it is important to measure and assess noise pollution and CO emissions and their effects and extent on human health. Therefore, the study aims to measure noise and CO emission from vehicles and to assess their impacts on human health in urban areas of Faisalabad.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Faisalabad is the third largest city of Pakistan and located in Punjab province. Due to industrial city it is very dense of population and vehicles; it's polluted with air pollution and noise pollution due to many industries and traffic. Heavy traffic like buses and trucks and small noisy traffic like rickshaws are running on non-well-constructed roads in this city. There is no standard value of different zones like commercial, residential and silence zones, people are building house and colonies on road side and also building schools and hospitals on road side so that they are affecting with air pollution and noise pollution.

Site Selections

Different locations were selected on the observations of noise and air pollution. Thirty different locations were selected for CO monitoring and forty locations were selected for noise monitoring in whole city, gap of ten locations is due to physical construction of roads and distance between these locations. These all locations were selected by the researcher one-week observations and then selected these all locations for proper research. These all locations were categorized in three different zones like commercial, residential and silence zones. Because standard of noise pollution and air pollution of vehicles is different in these three zones

Measurement sites

Locations for Noise Monitoring

Three categories of noise pollution locations were selected like commercial zone, residential zone and silence zones.

Commercial zone:

There are twenty locations were selected for commercial zone like,

1. Katchery Bazar
2. Chiniot Bazar
3. Amin Pur Bazar
4. Bhawana Baza
5. Jhag Bazar
6. karkhana Bazar
7. Mintgomery Bazar
8. Rail Bazar
9. Naranwala Chowk
10. DiglasPura Bazar
11. Lariadda
12. Gumti Chowk
13. GTS Chowk
14. Kohinoor plaza
15. Faizan E Madinasusan road
16. Saleemi chowk
17. D Ground
18. Abdullah pur pull chowk
19. MC Donald chowk
20. Metro Cash and carry

Residential zone:

There are ten sites were selected for noise measurement data like,

1. Peoples colony No 1
2. Madina town
3. Aminpur town canal road
4. University town

5. Lasani garden
6. G.M Abad
7. Tariq hall UAF
8. Fateh hall UAF
9. Jinah colony
10. Samanabad

Silence zone:

There were ten sites were measured for noise pollution in silent zone like,

1. Mujahid hospital
2. American doctors hospital
3. Punjab social security hospital
4. Mian Muhammad trust hospital
5. Khadija mahmood trust hospital
6. Hilal e ahmar hospital
7. Cardiology center
8. Allied hospital
9. Civil hospital
10. National hospital

Locations for CO measurement

Total thirty sites were measured for CO pollution in the city, further three different zones were selected for CO measurement, Faisalabad is industrial city so many industries are working in the main areas in city and causing air pollution so that one zone is different than noise monitoring in CO measurement like commercial zone, industrial zone and silence zone.

Commercial zone:

Sites of commercial zone for CO measurement almost same as noise measurement; so that three main locations were selected for CO which also has around fourteen sub locations same like noise measurement.

1. Clock tower
2. G.T.S Chowk
3. D.Ground

Silence zone

Silence zone for CO measurements included educational institute and hospitals like,

1. Punjab medical college
2. Allied hospital
3. University of Agriculture
4. Hilal e ahmar Hospital
5. G.C university
6. Punjab social security hospital

Industrial zone

Industrial zone for CO measurement is included different roads where industries also working, different types of industries established in this zone so that heavy traffic for loading materials like trucks and other vehicles also emitted CO in the air as well as industries chimneys.

1. Samundri road
2. Jhang road
3. Sargodha road
4. Sheikhupura road

Method of time, duration selection and Instrument used

For the measurement of CO and noise pollution as method of time, duration selection and instrument following methods were used.

1. Forty and thirty sites were measured for noise and CO measurement at three different zones, and industrial zone also measured in CO measurement.
2. For measurement of noise pollution two different times, morning and evening measurement was taken at same locations due to variation of vehicles on the roads at different time periods, but CO measurement was taken at peak time level.

3. Two different instruments were used to measured two different parameters, integrating sound level meter model 6226 was used to measure noise pollution and yellow fluke meter was used to measure CO level.
4. For this purpose of study these two meters were placed at tripod stand, sensors of meter pointed to the road sides and distance pointed from sources 1.5-meter height from the ground and sources.
5. Data was collected in june and july 2019 randomly selected days and statistically analyzed and compared with standard at every location.
6. Questionnaire Performa also filled from the people on the basis of their physical health due to this pollution.

Results

Noise pollution

Commercial zone

Twenty sites of commercial zone were selected for measurement of noise level in all locations, and then compared with NEQ'S level which is 65 db. Two times data was collected with these twenty sites first morning time start from 8 to 12 pm and then evening time start 12 pm to 8 pm to measure the maximum and minimum level of noise. The details of noise measured data is given in table 1 and further analysis of noise in these locations is determine in the graph plotted figure 1 and 2, noisy locations are determined on X-axis and noise level is determine on Y-axis.

This section may be divided by subheadings. It should provide a concise and precise description of the experimental results, their interpretation as well as the experimental conclusions that can be drawn.

Table 1. Measurement and Analysis of the traffic noise level in Commercial Zone

Locations	Morning (db)	Evening (db)	Average (db)	SD
Katchery Bazar	60	91	75.5	1.32
Chiniot Bazar	87	92	89.5	1.76
Amin Pur Bazar	72	89	80.5	3.77
Bhawana Bazar	77	90	83.5	3.98
Jhag Bazar	76	93	84.5	2.11
karkhana Bazar	79	85	82	2.12
Mintgomery Bazar	67	90	78.5	3.42
Rail Bazar	67	90	78.5	3.42
Naranwala Chowk	85	95	90	4.80
DiglasPura Bazar	85	91	88	2.12
Lariadda	80	98	89	4.40
Gumti Chowk	73	97	85	4.30
GTS Chowk	82	99	90.5	2.10
Kohinoor plaza	76	91	83.5	4.20
Faizan E MadinaSusan road	75	98	86.5	4.20
Saleemi chowk	72	96	84	4.00
D Ground	77	96	86.5	4.30
Abdullah pur pull chowk	83	99	91	4.60
MC Donald chowk	71	97	84	4.00
Metro Cash and carry	81	95	88	4.50

Figure 1. Traffic noise level at commercial zone

Figure 2. Traffic noise level at commercial zone

Residential zone

Ten sites were selected for traffic noise measurement in residential zone. Time of measurement noise was same as like commercial zone morning time and evening time, Because of people activity and traffic variations on the road two different time data was collected at the same locations. Further details and the traffic noise pollution is analyzed in the table 2 and in the figure 3.

Table 2. Measurement and Analysis of the traffic noise level in Residential zone

Locations	Morning (db)	Evening (db)	Average (db)	SD
Peoples colony No1	65	51	58.0	5.40
Madina town	60	52	56.0	2.82
Aminpur town canal road	75	50	62.5	3.60
University town	60	52	56.0	2.82
Lasani garden	79	52	65.5	2.10
G.M Abad	68	61	64.5	2.47
Tariq hall UAF	69	52	60.5	3.30
Fateh hall UAF	69	60	64.5	3.18
Jinah colony	63	51	57.0	2.10
Samanabad	81	50	65.5	2.43

Figure 3. Traffic noise level at residential zone

Silence zone

Ten sites of silent zone were measured for noise pollution in Faisalabad city. Silence zone is included different hospitals and some others institutes so that more noise is prohibited in these areas. Same like others two zone data was collected at morning and evening time at same locations. For further details and results of this study data is analyzed in table 3 and figure 4.

Table 3. Measurement and analysis of the traffic noise level in silence zone

Locations	Morning (db)	Evening (db)	Average (db)	SD
Mujahid hospital	80	78	79.0	0.707
American doctors' hospital	76	79	77.5	1.060
Punjab social security hospital	81	86	83.5	1.767
Mian Muhammad trust hospital	86	88	87.0	0.707
Khadija mahmood trust hospital	82	84	83.0	0.707
Hilal e ahmar hospital	86	88	87.0	0.707

Cardiology center	78	81	79.5	1.060
Allied hospital	85	83	84.0	0.707
Civil hospital	100	98	99.0	0.707
National hospital	80	83	81.5	1.060

Figure 4. Traffic noise level at silence zone

CO Measurements

CO emission in commercial zone

Noise pollution and CO emission from vehicles correlated with each other, because these both emissions depend on number of vehicles, if number of vehicles will increase then noise pollution and CO emission will also increase in that location. Figure 5 shows the emission of CO in commercial zone, data shows that in commercial zone maximum CO emissions were found in the evening time in all these locations.

Figure 5. Emission of CO in commercial zone (data presented mean \pm SD n=3)

CO emission in industrial zone

Figure 6 shows the concentration of CO emissions in industrial zone. Different four locations were measured in industrial zone; data shows that there is no big difference in this zone but maximum value 42 ppm was measured at Jhang road in the evening time and minimum value was 36 ppm at Samundri road. Similarly, in the morning time maximum value was 37 ppm at Jhang road and minimum value was 33 ppm at Samundri road.

Figure 6. Emission of CO in industrial zone (data presented mean \pm SD n=4)

CO emissions in silent zone

Concentration of CO emissions in silent zone shows in figure 7, Silent zone was separated in to two different parts educational institutes and hospitals. Maximum concentration

was 15 ppm of hospitals in the morning time and minimum concentration was 7 ppm of educational institute at same time, similarly in the evening time maximum concentration was measured 11 ppm at hospitals and minimum 5 ppm at educational institute.

Figure 7. Emission of CO in silent zone (data presented mean \pm SD n=2)

CO emission in Commercial, industrial and silent zone

Figure 8 shows the variation in all three zones, Maximum concentration was measured in industrial zone in the evening time as compared to morning time, but there is no big variation in this zone. Because in industrial zone there are so many industries are working and emit CO in the air as well as vehicles, this zone has two sources of CO emission industries and vehicles so that concentration of CO in this zone is more than other two zone. Commercial zone also has more concentration than silent zone; commercial zone has much density of vehicles as compared to silent zone, there are so many shopping's mall and others bus stop in this zone, so that this location is busy locations according with vehicles. Due to shopping mall people like to go evening time to shopping and for outing so that in commercial zone CO concentration is higher in evening time, Silent zone has less concentration of CO emission as compared to other two zone, there is big variation in this zone, hospitals has more CO concentration as educational institutes.

Figure 8. Compared of CO emission in commercial, industrial and silent zone (data presented mean \pm SD n=3)

Physical Effect of Noise pollution

There are two types of effects was measured of noise pollution such as,

- 1- Aggression
- 2- Depression, anxiety and stress

Aggression effect is like people behavior; around two hundred people behavior was checked to see the physical effect of noise pollution, figure 9 shows that 28% people was effected from noise pollution in aggression effect, 14% people was not effected with noise pollution in aggression behavior and 4% people don't know the effect of noise pollution. Similarly in depression, anxiety and stress effect of noise pollution 37% people was effected with noise pollution, 15% people was not effected with noise pollution and just 2% people don't know the effect of noise pollution on depression, anxiety and stress.

Figure 9. Assessment of physical effect of noise pollution

Health effect of CO emission

For the health effect of CO emission data was taken from the different hospitals and interviews of doctors in the hospital, around two hundreds interviews was conducted, this data was taken where the CO measurement was exceeding from limit. According to data figure 10 shows that 45% people was affected with respiratory disease due to CO pollution of vehicle emission. Similarly 32% people was effected with allergy, 35% giddiness, 50% ENT (Eyes and throat), and 42% people was affected from CO emissions from vehicles emission.

Figure 10. Assessment of health effect of CO emissions

Discussion

Table 1. shows that maximum value of noise was 87 db at chiniot bazar and minimum value was 60 db at kachery bazar in the morning time, this variation is due to different bazaar opening time and shopping time of people, chiniot bazaar has more noisy traffic than kachery bazaar in the morning time which exceed the standard limit. Similarly maximum value of noise was 99 db at Abdullah pur chowk location and minimum value was 85 db at karkhana Bazar in the evening time, and the average was as well as 91 and 82 db at same location which was greater than standard limit 65 db. According to Environmental protection agency Pakistan the noise limit in commercial zone is 70 db, but the average of all locations in these areas are greater than standard limit. Figure 1 shows also shows different variation of vehicle noise in different locations, maximum magnitude was ± 4.8 which shows the more fluctuation at naranwala chowk, because in this location there is a small bus and small transport vehicles stop and so many noisy rickshaws also making noise at this location. Figure 2 shows more fluctuation ± 4.5 at Abdullah pur chowk because this location is the route of heavy traffic and small noisy traffic like rickshaws. According to data analysis almost all locations of commercial zone declared noisy location and people are affected due to this noise pollution.

Table 2 shows that maximum value of noise pollution was 81 db at samnabad location, and minimum value was 60 db at two locations at university town and madina town in the morning time in the Faisalabad city. As well as in the evening time data shows that maximum value was 61 db at G.M abad colony and minimum value was 50 db at two locations samnabad and amin pur town canal road, and the maximum average of noise measurement is 65.5 db at two different locations samnabad and lasani garden and minimum average value is 56 db at madina town and university town. The data shows that maximum noise measured in the morning time because these are housing colonies and people move to work and offices at same time, but in the evening time noise values are not more larger than morning time because people different work off timing and came back home timing so that no more vehicles on the road in the evening time than morning time. Figure 3 shows maximum magnitude value is ± 3.6 at amin pur town canal road and minimum magnitude value is ± 5.4 and minimum magnitude value is ± 2.1 at two different locations. According to Environmental Protection Agency for motor vehicle exhaust and noise of Pakistan standard is 65 db for residential areas, data shows that maximum locations are considered as noisy locations due to unplanned living societies and roads constructed in these societies.

Table 3 shows that maximum value of noise pollution is 100 db at civil hospital location, which is greater than standard value, and minimum value is 76 db at American doctor's hospital in morning time. Similarly in evening time maximum noise level was 98 db at same location civil hospital and minimum level was 78 db at mujahid hospital. Maximum average of noise pollution was found at civil hospital 99 db which is 44 db greater than standard limit which is 55 db for silence zone. As well as minimum average of noise pollution was found 77.5 db at American doctor's hospital which is also 22.5 db level exceeded from standard value 55 db. In the figure 4 maximum magnitude values is ± 1.767767 at the Punjab social security hospital and minimum magnitude is ± 0.707107 at different six locations. According to Environmental Protection agency Pakistan standard of vehicle exhaust and noise value is 55 db for silence place. Data shows that silence place like hospitals of Faisalabad also unhealthy, noise pollution is affecting the people of these areas and also affecting of patients and doctors of these hospital due to noise pollution.

Figure 5 shows that maximum concentration of CO is 44 ppm in the evening time which is the highest and dangerous value of this location and minimum value is 32 ppm in clock tower

location in the evening time. Similarly in the morning time maximum concentration is 29 ppm at Clock tower location and minimum is 18 ppm at GTS chowk location in the morning time. So data shows that maximum concentration of CO emission is in evening time but CO emission is exceeded in all location and both evening and morning time because the standard value of CO vehicle emission is 5 ppm. Figure 6 shows that all locations data is non significant effect, because all these locations have no big difference and all are exceeded from standard value. Figure 7 show that two different locations has big difference of CO measurement so data has significantly difference in silent zone. CO measurement data shows the big difference in all three zones, maximum CO was measured in industrial zone in the evening time, and minimum concentration was measured at silent zone.

A questionnaire performa was filled by the people to check the physical health and other disease of noise pollution and CO emission. Maximum 37% people affected with depression, anxiety and stress due to noise pollution, and maximum 50% people affected with ENT due to CO emission. This performa was filled during the other data was collected at the same locations; mostly performa was filled by the people at that locations where pollution was exceeding from standard limit.

Conclusion

Irregular rush of vehicles, old big vehicles, and small auto rickshaws are major problem of CO emission and noise pollution in Faisalabad, Pakistan. Transportation system is not good in this city, mostly in city people use auto rickshaws for travelling which is too much noisy and emit CO in the environment. Some developed city like Islamabad, Pakistan has banned these kinds of vehicles like auto rickshaws. Study shows that mostly locations exceeded the standard limit of noise pollution and CO emission, most of the locations exceeded 70 to 90 db of noise pollution in the evening time and 60 to 90 in the morning time, similarly CO emission was also exceeded from standard limit of EPA (Environmental Protection Agency) of Pakistan, and maximum value was 15 to 25 ppm at mostly location in the evening time and 10 to 20 ppm value was at morning time. So the study shows that both of pollution is affecting the health of people living in this city. During the study survey shows that mostly people are affecting with these pollutions, health issues are increasing due to these effects of noise pollution and CO emission. A study in 2019 was conducted on just noise pollution, on that study there were many different

locations at different time, 85 different locations were measured at different time like morning, noon and evening, just one time one location was measured, some locations was measured at morning time and some at noon and some at evening [45]. But in this study same location was measured at twice time to know the average of noise at that locations and at same time and same location also checked the CO emission because these two parameters has co- relation with each others. With measuring these two pollution data author also check the physical and others health effect of people related with these two pollution by questionnaire Performa. So author try to fill the gap of before studied and in the future others gaps of study will also discuss others hazardous gases like CO emission, because vehicles also emit others hazardous gases.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Reverence:

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